

Performance Evaluation of a Medium Grade Low Heat Rejection Diesel Engine with Mohr Oil Based Bio-Diesel

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ABSTRACT

Investigations were carried out to evaluate the performance of a low heat rejection (LHR) diesel engine with air gap insulated piston with supermi (an alloy of nickel) and air gap insulated liner with different operating conditions [normal temperature and pre-heated temperature] of mohr oil based bio-diesel (MOBD) with varied injection pressure and injection timing. Performance parameters and exhaust emissions of smoke and oxides of nitrogen (NOx) were determined at different magnitudes of brake mean effective pressure (BMEP). Combustion characteristics at peak load operation of the engine were measured with TDC (top dead centre) encoder, pressure transducer, console and special pressure-crank angle software package. Conventional engine (CE) showed marginal improvement in performance with biodiesel operation, while LHR engine showed improved performance at recommended injection timing of 27°bTDC (before top dead centre) and recommended injection pressure of 190 bar. The performance of both version of the engine improved with advanced injection timing and at higher injection pressure when compared with CE with pure diesel operation. The optimum injection timing was 33°bTDC for CE while it was 31°bTDC with LHR engine with biodiesel operation. Peak brake thermal efficiency increased by 12.5%, smoke levels decreased by 48% and NOx levels increased by 35% with MOBD operation on LHR engine at its optimum injection timing, when compared with pure diesel operation on CE at 27°bTDC.

Key word

Mohr oil, Esterification, LHR engine, Performance, Emissions, Combustion characteristics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Diesel fuel is consumed in not only transport sector but also in agricultural sector. These fuels are fossil in nature, leads to the depletion of fuel. Pollution levels are increasing with the fossil fuels. And also there is burden on Govt. of India in importing crude oils. In the context of depletion of fossil fuels, the search for alternate and renewable fuels has become pertinent. It has been found that the vegetable oil is a promising fuel, because of its properties are similar to those of diesel

fuel and it is a renewable and can be easily produced. Rudolph diesel, the inventor of the engine that bears his name, experimented with fuels ranging from powdered coal to peanut oil. Experiments were conducted¹⁻⁴ with CE with crude vegetable oils and reported that performance was deteriorated with CE, as these oils have high viscosity, low volatility and polyunsaturated character. The higher viscosity of the oil affects the spray pattern spray angle, droplet size, droplet distribution. Not only that, the common problems of crude vegetable oils in diesel engines are formation of carbon deposits, oil ring sticking, thickening and gelling of lubricating oil as a result of contamination by the vegetable oils. The fatty present in vegetable oils like palmitic, steric, lingoceric, oleic and linoleic etc, increase smoke emissions and also lead to incomplete combustion due to improper air-fuel mixing. These problems can be solved, if neat vegetable oils are chemically modified to bio-diesel. Biodiesels derived from vegetable oils present a very promising alternative to diesel fuel since biodiesels have numerous advantages compared to fossil fuels as they are renewable, biodegradable, provide energy security and foreign exchange savings besides addressing environmental concerns and socio-economic issues. Experiments were carried out⁵⁻¹⁰ with biodiesel on CE and reported performance was compatible with pure diesel operation on CE. The internal combustion engines that presently depend on fossil fuels need to be redesigned and optimized for greater efficiencies and lower emissions. The drawbacks of the biodiesel call for hot combustion chamber provided by low heat rejection (LHR) diesel engine. The concept of LHR engine is to provide thermal insulation in the path of heat flow to the coolant and increase thermal efficiency of the engine. LHR engines are classified into low grade, medium grade and high grade engines depending on degree of insulation. Low grade engines consist of thermal coatings on piston, liner, cylinder head and other engine components, medium grade engines provide an air gap in the piston and other components with low-thermal conductivity materials like superni, cast iron and mild steel etc and high grade engines are combination of low and medium grade engines. Ceramic coatings provided adequate insulation and improved brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC) which was reported by various researchers¹¹⁻¹⁷. Air gap was created¹⁸ in the nimonic piston crown and experiments were conducted with pure diesel and reported that BSFC increased by 7% with varied injection timings. Investigations were carried¹⁹ with air gap insulated piston with superni crown and air gap insulated liner with superni insert with varied injection pressures and injection timings with alternate fuels of alcohols and vegetable oils and reported LHR engine improved efficiency and decreased pollution levels. Experiments were conducted²⁰ on high grade LHR engine with jatropha oil and pongamia oil based biodiesel with varied injection timing and pressure and reported high grade LHR engine improved thermal efficiency and decreased pollution levels.

Little literature was available in evaluating the performance of LHR engine with air gap insulated piston and air gap insulated liner with varying engine parameters at different operating conditions of the MOBD. The present paper attempted to evaluate the performance of LHR engine, which contained an air gap insulated piston and air gap insulated liner at different operating conditions of MOBD with varying engine parameters of change of injection pressure and timing and compared with CE with pure diesel operation at recommended injection timing and injection pressure.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

The term Esterification means conversion of one ester into the other. In the present case glycerol was replaced with methyl alcohol, the fatty acids remaining the same. The chemical conversion reduced viscosity four fold. As it is evident glycerol was the byproduct of the reaction and a valuable commercial commodity. The process¹⁹ of converting the oil into methyl esters was carried out by heating the crude vegetable oil with the methanol in the presence of the catalyst (Sodium hydroxide). In the present case, biodiesel (Mohr oil) was stirred with methanol at around 60-70°C with 0.5% of NaOH based on weight of the oil, for about 3 hours. At the end of the reaction, excess methanol was removed by distillation and glycerol, which separates out was

removed. The methyl esters were treated with dilute acid to neutralize the alkali and then washed to get free of acid, dried and distilled to get pure biodiesel esters. The esters were used in present study. The properties of biodiesel were given in Table-1 along with diesel fuel. Fig.1 gave the details of insulated piston and insulated liner employed in the experimentation. The LHR diesel engine contained a two-part piston - the top crown made of low thermal conductivity material, superni-90 was screwed to aluminum body of the piston, providing a 3-mm-air gap in between the crown and the body of the piston. The optimum thickness of air gap in the air gap piston was found¹⁸ to be 3-mm for better performance of the engine with superni inserts with diesel as fuel. A superni-90 insert was screwed to the top portion of the liner in such a manner that an air gap of 3-mm was maintained between the insert and the liner body.

Table 1. Properties of the Test Fuels

Test Fuel	Viscosity at 25°C (Centi-poise)	Density at 25°C	Cetane number	Calorific value (kJ/kg)
Diesel	12.5	0.84	55	42000
Mohr oil (esterified)	53	0.87	55	37500

Figure 1. Assembly details of insulated piston and insulated liner

Experimental setup used for the investigations of LHR diesel engine with MOBD was shown in Fig.2. CE had an aluminum alloy piston with a bore of 80-mm and a stroke of 110-mm. The rated output of the engine was 3.68 kW at a speed of 1500 rpm. The compression ratio was 16:1 and manufacturer's recommended injection timing and injection pressures were 27°bTDC and

190 bar respectively. The fuel injector had 3-holes of size 0.25-mm. The combustion chamber consisted of a direct injection type with no special arrangement for swirling motion of air. The engine was connected to electric dynamometer for measuring its brake power. Burette method was used for finding fuel consumption of the engine. Air-consumption of the engine was measured by air-box method.

1.Engine, 2.Electical Dynamo meter, 3.Load Box, 4.Orifice meter, 5.U-tube water manometer, 6.Air box, 7.Fuel tank, 8, Pre-heater, 9.Burette, 10. Exhaust gas temperature indicator, 11.AVL Smoke meter, 12.Netel Chromatograph NO_x Analyzer, 13.Outlet jacket water temperature indicator, 14. Outlet-jacket water flow meter, 15.Piezo-electric pressure transducer, 16.Console, 17.TDC encoder, 18.Pentium Personal Computer and 19. Printer.

Figure 2. Experimental Set-up

The naturally aspirated engine was provided with water-cooling system in which inlet temperature of water was maintained at 60°C by adjusting the water flow rate. Engine oil was provided with a pressure feed system. No temperature control was incorporated, for measuring the lube oil temperature. Copper shims of suitable size were provided in between the pump body and the engine frame, to vary the injection timing and its effect on the performance of the engine was studied, along with the change of injection pressures from 190 bar to 270 bar (in steps of 40 bar) using nozzle testing device. The maximum injection pressure was restricted to 270 bar due to practical difficulties involved. Exhaust gas temperature (EGT) was measured with thermocouples made of iron and iron-Constantan. Pollution levels of smoke and NO_x were recorded by AVL smoke meter and Netel Chromatograph NO_x analyzer respectively at the peak load operation of the engine. Piezo electric transducer, fitted on the cylinder head to measure pressure in the combustion chamber was connected to a console, which in turn was connected to Pentium personal computer. TDC encoder provided at the extended shaft of the dynamometer was connected to the console to measure the crank angle of the engine. A special P-θ software package evaluated the combustion characteristics such as peak pressure (PP), time of occurrence of peak pressure (TOPP), maximum rate of pressure rise (MRPR) and time of occurrence of maximum rate of pressure rise (TOMRPR) from the signals of pressure and crank angle at the peak load operation of the engine. Pressure-crank angle diagram was obtained on the screen of the personal computer.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Performance Parameters

Fig.3 showed the variation of brake thermal efficiency (BTE) with brake mean effective pressure (BMEP) in the conventional engine (CE) with MOBD at an injection pressure of 190 bar at various injection timings. From the Fig.3, it could be noticed that, CE with biodiesel showed compatible performance for entire load range when compared with the pure diesel operation on CE at recommended injection timing. Although carbon accumulations on the nozzle tip might play a partial role for the general trends observed, the difference of viscosity between the diesel and biodiesel provided a possible explanation for the compatible performance with biodiesel operation.

Figure3. Variation of brake thermal efficiency (BTE) with brake mean effective pressure (BMEP) in conventional engine (CE) at different injection timings with mohr oil based bio diesel (MOBD) oil operation at an injection pressure of 190 bar.

The performance of CE with biodiesel was compatible with pure diesel operation on CE, as its properties are similar particularly Cetane number to those of diesel fuel. BTE increased with the advancing of the injection timing in CE with the biodiesel at all loads, when compared with CE at the recommended injection timing and pressure. This was due to initiation of combustion at earlier period and efficient combustion with increase of air entrainment in fuel spray giving higher BTE. BTE increased at all loads when the injection timing was advanced to 33°bTDC in the CE at the normal temperature of biodiesel. The increase of BTE at optimum injection timing over the recommended injection timing with biodiesel with CE could be attributed to its longer ignition delay and combustion duration. BTE increased at all loads when the injection timing was advanced to 33°bTDC in CE, at the preheated temperature of MOBD. That, too, the performance improved further in CE with the preheated biodiesel for entire load range when compared with normal biodiesel. Preheating of the biodiesel reduced the viscosity, which improved the spray characteristics of the biodiesel and reduced the impingement of the fuel spray on combustion chamber walls, causing efficient combustion thus improving BTE.

Fig.4 showed the variation of BTE with BMEP in the LHR engine with MOBD, at various injection timings at an injection pressure of 190 bar. From the Fig.4, it could be observed that

LHR version of the engine showed improvement in the performance for entire load range compared with CE with pure diesel operation.

Figure 4. Variation of BTE with BMEP in LHR engine at different injection timings with MOBD operation.

High cylinder temperatures helped in better evaporation and faster combustion of the fuel injected into the combustion chamber. Reduction of ignition delay of the biodiesel in the hot environment of the LHR engine improved heat release rates and efficient energy utilization. Preheating of biodiesel improved performance further in LHR version of the engine. The optimum injection timing was found to be 31°bTDC with LHR engine with normal MOBD. Since the hot combustion chamber of LHR engine reduced ignition delay and combustion duration and hence the optimum injection timing was obtained earlier with LHR engine when compared with CE with the biodiesel operation.

Fig.5 showed the variation of BTE with BMEP in CE and LHR engine with MOBD at normal temperature at the recommended and optimized injection timings at an injection pressure of 190 bar. From Fig.5 it could be observed that, at optimum injection timing, BTE with LHR engine at its optimum injection timing was higher than that of CE. Decrease of combustion duration and better evaporation rates would help in increasing the efficiency of LHR engine. The advantage of LHR engine was obvious for burning high viscous biodiesel.

Figure 5. Variation of BTE with BMEP in different versions of the engine at the recommended injection timing and optimum injection timing at an injection pressure of 190 bar.

Injection pressure was varied from 190 bars to 270 bars to improve the spray characteristics and atomization of the biodiesel and injection timing was advanced from 27 to 34°bTDC for CE and LHR engine. Table.2 showed the variation of peak BTE which varied with injection timing and injection pressure in CE and LHR engine at different operating conditions of the biodiesel. From Table-2, it could be noticed that BTE increased with increase in injection pressure in both versions of the engine at different operating conditions of the biodiesel. The improvement in BTE at higher injection pressure was due to improved fuel spray characteristics. However, the optimum injection timing was not varied even at higher injection pressure with LHR engine, unlike the CE. Hence it was concluded that the optimum injection timing was 33°bTDC at 190 bar, 32°bTDC at 230 bar and 31°bTDC at 270 bar for CE. The optimum injection timing for LHR engine was 31°bTDC irrespective of injection pressure. Peak BTE was higher in LHR engine when compared with CE with different operating conditions of the biodiesel.

Table 2. Data of peak BTE

Injection Timing (° bTDC)	Test Fuel	Peak BTE (%)											
		Conventional Engine (CE)						LHR Engine					
		Injection Pressure (Bar)						Injection Pressure (Bar)					
		190		230		270		190		230		270	
		NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT
27	DF	28	--	29	---	30	--	29	--	30	--	30.5	--
	MOBD	28	29	29	30	30	31	29.5	30	30	30.5	30.5	31
29	DF	28.5	--	29.5	--	30.2		29.5	--	30.5	--	31	--
	MOBD	29	29.5	29.5	30	30	30.5	30	30.5	30.5	31	31	31.5
30	DF	29	---	30	--	30.5	--	29	--	30	--	30.5	--
	MOBD	29.5	30	30	30.5	30.5	31	30.5	31	31	31.5	31.5	32
31	DF	29.5	--	30	--	31	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
	MOBD	30	30.5	30.5	31	31	31.5	31.5	32	32	32.5	32.5	33
32	DF	30		30.5		30.5							
	MOBD	30.5	31	31	31.5	31	31.5	--	--	--	--	--	--
33	DF	31		31		30							
	MOBD	31	31.5	31.5	32	32	32.5	--	--	--	--	--	--

DF-Diesel Fuel, MOBD- Mohr oil based bio-diesel, NT- Normal or Room Temperature , PT- Preheat Temperature

Fig.6 showed the variation of the exhaust gas temperature (EGT) with BMEP in CE and LHR engine with MOBD at normal temperature at the recommended and optimized injection timings at an injection pressure of 190 bar. From the Fig.6, it could be observed that CE with MOBD at the recommended injection timing recorded marginally higher EGT at all loads compared with CE with pure diesel operation. Lower heat release rates and retarded heat release associated with high specific energy consumption caused increase in EGT in CE. Ignition delay in the CE with different operating conditions of biodiesel increased the duration of the burning phase.

Figure 6. Variation of exhaust gas temperature (EGT) with BMEP in CE and LHR engine at recommend injection timing and optimized injection timings with MOBD operation.

LHR engine recorded lower value of EGT when compared with CE with biodiesel operation. This was due to reduction of ignition delay in the hot environment with the provision of the insulation in the LHR engine, which caused the gases expanded in the cylinder giving higher work output and lower heat rejection. This showed that the performance improved with LHR engine over CE with biodiesel operation. The magnitude of EGT at peak load decreased with advancing of injection timing and with increase of injection pressure in both versions of the engine with biodiesel. Preheating of the biodiesel further reduced the magnitude of EGT, compared with normal biodiesel in both versions of the engine.

Table.3 showed the variation of EGT at peak load operation with injection timing and injection pressure in CE and LHR engine at different operating conditions of the biodiesel. From the Table-3, it could be noticed that EGT decreased with increase in injection pressure and injection timing with both versions of the engine, which confirmed that performance increased with increase of injection pressure. Preheating of biodiesel decreased EGT in both versions of the engine.

Table 3. Data of EGT at peak load operation

Injection timing (° b TDC)	Test Fuel	EGT at the peak load (°C)											
		CE						LHR Engine					
		Injection Pressure (Bar)						Injection Pressure (Bar)					
		190		230		270		190		230		270	
		NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT
27	DF	425	--	410	---	395	--	460	---	450	--	440	--
	MOBD	450	425	425	400	400	375	400	375	375	350	350	325
29	DF							440		430		420	
	MOBD	425	400	400	375	375	350	380	360	360	340	340	320
30	DF	410	---	400	--	385	---	460	---	450	--	440	--
	MOBD	400	375	375	350	400	375	360	340	340	320	320	300
31	DF	400	---	390	--	375	---	450	---	445	---	440	---
	MOBD	375	350	360	340	350	325	340	320	320	300	300	280
32	DF	390		380		380							--
	MOBD	360	340	350	325	360	340	-----	---	---	----	---	-
33	DF	375	---	375	---	400	--	--	--	--	---	--	--
	MOBD	350	325	360	340	370	350						

Fig.7 showed the variation of the volumetric efficiency (VE) with BMEP in CE and LHR engine with MOBD at the recommended and optimized injection timings at an injection pressure of 190 bar. From Fig.7, it could be noticed that volumetric efficiency (VE) decreased with an increase of BMEP in both versions of the engine. This was due to increase of gas temperature with the load. At the recommended injection timing, VE in the both versions of the engine with MOBD operation decreased at all loads when compared with CE with pure diesel operation. This was due to increase of deposits with biodiesel operation with CE. With LHR engine, this was due increase of temperature of incoming charge in the hot environment created with the provision of insulation, causing reduction in the density and hence the quantity of air with LHR engine. VE increased marginally in CE and LHR engine at optimized injection timings when compared with recommended injection timing with MOBD. This was due to decrease of un-burnt fuel fraction in the cylinder leading to increase in VE in CE and reduction of gas temperatures with LHR engine.

VE decreased relatively by 6.5% with LHR engine at its optimized injection timing when compared with pure diesel operation on CE.

Figure 7. Variation of volumetric efficiency (VE) with BMEP in CE and LHR engine at recommend injection timing and optimized injection timings with MOBD operation at an injection pressure of 190 bar.

Table.4 showed the variation of volumetric efficiency at peak load operation with injection timing and injection pressure in CE and LHR engine at different operating conditions of the biodiesel. VE increased with increase of injection pressure and with advanced injection timing in both versions of the engine. This was also due to better fuel spray characteristics and evaporation at higher injection pressures leading to marginal increase of VE. This was also due to the reduction of residual fraction of the fuel, with the increase of injection pressure. Preheating of the biodiesel marginally improved VE in both versions of the engine, because of reduction of un-burnt fuel concentration with efficient combustion, when compared with the normal temperature of oil.

Table 4. Data of VE at peak load operation

Injection timing (° bTDC)	Test Fuel	Volumetric efficiency (%)											
		CE						LHR Engine					
		Injection Pressure (Bar)						Injection Pressure (Bar)					
		190		230		270		190		230		270	
		NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT
27	DF	85	--	86	--	87	--	78	--	80	--	82	--
	MOBD	83	84	84	85	85	86	75.5	76.5	76.5	77.5	77.5	78.5
29	DF	86		87		88		78.5		80.5		82.5	
	MOBD	84	85	85	86	86	87	77	77.5	78.5	79.5	79.5	80.5
30	DF	86	--	87	--	88	--	76	--	77	--	78	--
	MOBD	85	86	86	87	85	86	78	78.5	78.5	79	79	79.5
31	DF	87	--	87.5	--	89	--						
	MOBD	86	87	85	86	88	89	79	79.5	79.5	80	80	81
32	DF	87.5	--	88	--	87	--	-	--	-	--	--	-
	MOBD	87	88	88	89	87	88	--	--	--	--	--	--
33	DF	89		90		91							
	MOBD	88	89	88	89	88.5	89.5	--	--	--	--	--	--

3.2 Exhaust Emissions

Fig.8 showed the variation of the smoke levels in Hartridge smoke unit (HSU) with BMEP in CE and LHR engine with biodiesel operation at the recommended and optimized injection timings at an injection pressure of 190 bar. From Fig.8, it could be noticed that drastic increase of smoke levels was observed at the peak load operation in CE at different operating conditions of the biodiesel, compared with pure diesel operation on CE.

Figure 8. Variation of smoke intensity in Hartridge Smoke Unit (HSU) with BMEP in CE and LHR engine at recommend injection timing and optimized injection timings with MOBD at an injection pressure of 190 bar.

This was due to the higher magnitude of the ratio of C/H of MOBD (0.78) when compared with pure diesel (0.45). The increase of smoke levels was also due to decrease of air-fuel ratios and VE with biodiesel compared with pure diesel operation. Smoke levels were related to the density of the fuel. Since biodiesel has higher density compared to diesel fuels, smoke levels are higher with biodiesel. However, LHR engine marginally reduced smoke levels due to efficient combustion and less amount of fuel accumulation on the hot combustion chamber walls of the LHR engine at different operating conditions of the biodiesel compared with the CE. Density influences the fuel injection system. Decreasing the fuel density tends to increase spray dispersion and spray penetration. Preheating of the biodiesels reduced smoke levels in both versions of the engine, when compared with normal temperature of the biodiesel. This was due to i) the reduction of density of the biodiesels, as density was directly proportional to smoke levels, ii) the reduction of the diffusion combustion proportion in CE with the preheated biodiesel, iii) the reduction of the viscosity of the biodiesel, with which the fuel spray does not impinge on the combustion chamber walls of lower temperatures rather than it directed into the combustion chamber.

Table.5 showed the variation of Smoke Levels at peak load operation with injection timing and injection pressure in CE and LHR engine at different operating conditions of the biodiesel. From Table-5, it could be noticed that smoke levels decreased with increase of injection timings and with increase of injection pressure, in both versions of the engine, with different operating conditions of the biodiesel.

Table 5. Data of smoke levels at peak load operation

Injection timing (°bTDC)	Test Fuel	Smoke intensity (HSU)											
		CE						LHR Engine					
		Injection Pressure (Bar)						Injection Pressure (Bar)					
		190		230		270		190		230		270	
		NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT
27	DF	48	--	38	--	34	--	55	--	50	--	45	--
	MOBD	60	55	55	50	50	45	45	40	40	35	35	30
29	DF	40	--	36	--	34							
	MOBD	55	50	50	45	45	40	40	35	35	30	30	25
30	DF	36	--	34	--	32	--	45	--	42	--	41	--
	MOBD	50	45	45	40	50	45	35	30	30	25	25	20
31	DF	33	---	32	--	30	--	43	--	41	--	40	--
	MOBD	45	40	40	35	35	32	30	25	25	20	20	18
32	DF	32	--	31	--	32	--	--	--	--	---	--	--
	MOBD	40	35	35	32	40	35	--	--	--	--	---	-
33	DF	30	---	30	--	35	--	-	--	--	--	--	--
	MOBD	35	32	40	35	42	37						

This was due to improvement in the fuel spray characteristics at higher injection pressures and increase of air entrainment, at the advanced injection timings, causing lower smoke levels.

Fig.9 showed the variation of the NOx levels with BMEP in CE and LHR engine with biodiesel operation at the recommended and optimized injection timings at an injection pressure of 190 bar. From Fig.9, it could be noticed that NOx levels were lower in CE while they were higher in LHR engine at different operating conditions of the biodiesel at the peak load when compared with diesel operation. This was due to lower heat release rate because of high duration of combustion

causing lower gas temperatures with the biodiesel operation on CE, which reduced NO_x levels. Increase of combustion temperatures with the faster combustion and improved heat release rates in LHR engine caused higher NO_x levels. As expected, preheating of the biodiesel decreased NO_x levels in both versions of the engine when compared with the normal biodiesel. This was due to improved air fuel ratios and decrease of combustion temperatures leading to decrease NO_x emissions in the CE and decrease of combustion temperatures in the LHR engine with the improvement in air-fuel ratios leading to decrease NO_x levels in LHR engine.

Figure 9. Variation of NO_x levels with BMEP in CE and LHR engine at recommend injection timing and optimized injection timings with MOBD operation at an injection pressure of 190 bar.

Table.6 showed the variation of NO_x Levels at peak load operation with injection timing and injection pressure in CE and LHR engine at different operating conditions of the biodiesel. From Table-6, it could be observed that NO_x levels increased with the advancing of the injection timing in CE with different operating conditions of biodiesel.

Table 6. Data of NOx levels at peak load operation

Injection timing (° b TDC)	Test Fuel	NOx levels (ppm)											
		CE						LHR Engine					
		Injection Pressure (Bar)						Injection Pressure (Bar)					
		190		230		270		190		230		270	
		NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT
27	DF	850	----	810	----	770	---	1300	--	1280	--	1260	--
	MOBD	800	750	750	700	700	650	1300	1250	1250	1200	1200	1150
29	DF	900	--	860	--	820	--						
	MOBD	850	800	800	750	750	700	1250	1200	1200	1150	1150	1100
30	DF	935	---	900	---	860	--	1225	--	1205	--	1185	--
	MOBD	900	850	850	800	800	750	1200	1150	1150	1100	1100	1050
31	DF	1020	---	980	---	940	---	1150	--	1130	--	1110	--
	MOBD	950	900	900	850	850	800	1150	1100	1100	1050	1050	1000
32	DF	1105	----	1060	---	1020	---	--	--	--	--	--	--
	MOBD	1000	950	950	900	900	850	--	-	--	--	--	-
33	DF	1190	----	1150	---	1110	---	--	--	--	--	--	-
	MOBD	1050	1000	1000	950	950	900						

Residence time and availability of oxygen had increased, when the injection timing was advanced with the biodiesel operation, which caused higher NOx levels in CE. However, NOx levels decreased with increase of injection pressure in CE. With the increase of injection pressure, fuel droplets penetrate and find oxygen counterpart easily. Turbulence of the fuel spray increased the spread of the droplets which caused decrease of gas temperatures marginally thus leading to decrease in NOx levels. Marginal decrease of NOx levels was observed in LHR engine, due to decrease of combustion temperatures, which was evident from the fact that thermal efficiency was increased in LHR engine due to the reason sensible gas energy was converted into actual work in LHR engine, when the injection timing was advanced and with increase of injection pressure.

3.3 Combustion Characteristics

Table.7 showed the comparison on the magnitudes of PP, MRPR, TOPP and TOMRPR with the injection timing and injection pressure, at the peak load operation of CE and LHR engine with biodiesel operation. From Table-7, it could be observed peak pressures were compatible in CE while they were higher in LHR engine at the recommended injection timing and pressure with biodiesel operation, when compared with pure diesel operation on CE. This was due to increase of ignition delay, as biodiesels require large duration of combustion. Mean while the piston started making downward motion thus increasing volume when the combustion takes place in CE. LHR engine increased the mass-burning rate of the fuel in the hot environment leading to produce higher peak pressures. The advantage of using LHR engine for biodiesel was obvious as it could burn low Cetane and high viscous fuels. Peak pressures increased with the increase of injection pressure and with the advancing of the injection timing in both versions of the engine, with the biodiesel operation. Higher injection pressure produced smaller fuel particles with low surface to volume ratio, giving rise to higher PP. With the advancing of the injection timing to the optimum value with the CE, more amount of the fuel accumulated in the combustion chamber due to increase of ignition delay as the fuel spray found the air at lower pressure and temperature in the combustion chamber. When the fuel- air mixture burns, it produces more combustion temperatures and pressures due to increase of the mass of the fuel. With LHR engine, peak pressures increases due to effective utilization of the charge with the advancing of the injection

timing to the optimum value. The magnitude of TOPP decreased with the advancing of the injection timing and with increase of injection pressure in both versions of the engine, at different operating conditions of biodiesels. TOPP was more with different operating conditions of biodiesels in CE, when compared with pure diesel operation on CE. This was due to higher ignition delay with the biodiesel when compared with pure diesel fuel. This once again established the fact by observing lower peak pressures and higher TOPP, that CE with biodiesel operation showed the deterioration in the performance when compared with pure diesel operation on CE. Preheating of the biodiesel showed lower TOPP, compared with biodiesel at normal temperature. This once again confirmed by observing the lower TOPP and higher PP, the performance of the both versions of the engine improved with the preheated biodiesel compared with the normal biodiesel.

Table 7. Data of PP, MRPR, TOPP and TOMRPR at peak load operation

Injection timing (°bTDC) Test fuel	Engine version	PP(bar)				MRPR (Bar/deg)				TOPP (Deg)				TOMRPR (Deg)			
		Injection pressure (Bar)				Injection pressure (Bar)				Injection pressure (Bar)				Injection pressure (Bar)			
		190		270		190		270		190		270		190		270	
		NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT	NT	PT
27/Diesel	CE	50.4	--	53.5	--	3.1	--	3.4	--	9	-	8	--	0	0	0	0
	LHR	48.1	--	53.0	--	2.9	--	3.1	--	10	--	9	--	0	0	0	0
27/ MOBD	CE	48.9	50.9	51.1	52.4	2.2	2.3	2.9	3.0	11	10	11	9	1	1	1	1
	LHR	58.8	59.7	62.1	63.8	3.2	3.3	3.4	3.4	10	9	9	8	1	1	1	1
31/MOBD	LHR	61.5	62.8	64.1	64.8	3.6	3.8	3.8	3.9	9	8	8	8	0	0	0	0
33/MOBD	CE	53.3	54.6			3.5	3.7			10	9			0	0		

This trend of increase of MRPR and decrease of TOMRPR indicated better and faster energy substitution and utilization by biodiesels, which could replace 100% diesel fuel. However, these combustion characters were within the limits hence the biodiesels could be effectively substituted for diesel fuel

4. CONCLUSIONS

Biodiesel operation at 27°bTDC on CE showed the compatible performance, while LHR engine showed improved performance, when compared with pure diesel operation on CE. Preheating of the biodiesel improved performance when compared with normal biodiesel in both versions of the engine. Improvement in the performance was observed with the advancing of the injection timing and with the increase of injection pressure with the biodiesel operation on both versions of the engine. CE with biodiesel operation showed the optimum injection timing at 33°bTDC, while the LHR engine showed the optimum injection at 31°bTDC at an injection pressure of 190 bars. At the recommended injection timing and pressure, biodiesel operation on CE increased smoke levels, decreased NOx levels, while LHR engine decreased smoke levels and increased NOx levels when compared with pure diesel operation on CE. Preheating of the biodiesel decreased smoke levels and NOx levels slightly in both versions of the engine. CE with biodiesel operation decreased smoke levels and increased NOx levels, while LHR engine decreased smoke and NOx levels with the advancing of the injection timing. With increase in injection pressure, smoke and NOx levels decreased in both versions of the engine. Lower peak pressures and more TOPP were observed with normal biodiesel in CE. LHR engine with biodiesel operation increased PP and

decreased TOPP when compared with CE. Preheating increased PP and decreased TOPP when compared with normal biodiesel operation on both versions of the engine. Compatible peak pressures were observed in CE, while higher peak pressures in the LHR engine with biodiesel operation at the recommended injection timing and pressure.

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